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Distributed analysis on human data supported by semantic models and GA4GH specifications

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Abstract

This poster presents a toolbox for implementing and validating a set of scenarios for federated and distributed analysis with synthetic data. The scenarios focus on analysing genomic variations across patients to assist in profiling them for treatment and to support research on rare diseases. The toolbox is composed of software components, specifications and synthetic data that have been used and implemented in the intersection of several European projects and aim to bridge the gap between syntactical standards and semantic web technologies.

The poster will highlight how a resource connected to the Virtual Platform of the European Joint Programme on Rare diseases can register services and data shapes to support data discovery and query design for subsequent analysis through data visitation. It will also showcase how the European Genomic Data Infrastructure project's Starter Kit can be configured with the FAIR Data Point Reference Implementation and computational notebooks to create a flexible playground for designing compelling demonstrators on federated access to human data. Furthermore, it will illustrate how the corresponding open technical specifications from the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health and the World Wide Web Consortium enables flexible reconfiguration of the toolbox for different deployment scenarios.

Keywords

federated human data, semantic web technologies, interoperability